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FILTRATION STUDIES OF COMPOSITIONS ON CORE SAMPLES UNDER CONDITIONS CLOSE TO REAL DATA ON DEPOSITS OF WESTERN KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

This article discusses filtration studies of compositions on core samples under conditions close to real conditions for the deposit of JSC Embanefit Vostochny Moldabek. Core material of well No. 2205 was selected for the productive horizon M-II. A two-phase vertical filtration plant (LXRT-400T) was used to determine the filtration-capacitance properties (FCP) of reservoir rocks using a model of reservoir water and oil. This equipment is designed to study saturation profiles during filtration of two-phase flows in reservoir conditions in real time, representing average saturation as a function of core length and discrete points along the core as a function of time.

Keywords: Core, formation, horizon, well, research, filtration and capacitance properties (FCP).

The procedure for conducting research on a two-phase filtration unit with X-ray saturation control, the sequence and technique of conducting filtration experiments do not differ from the main provisions of existing methods and industry standards.

In the LXRT-400T system, the core holder is mounted in an upright position so that it can be scanned by a trolley mounted with an X-ray source and receiver system to monitor fluid saturation during the inflow test.

To determine the saturation profile of the core sample under study, the latter is placed in the core holder. Then the generator and the X-ray detector are switched on, which moves along the rail guides along the sample at a given speed and at certain intervals the detector registers the X-ray radiation that has passed through the sample. The signal received by the radiation detector is processed and output to the monitor in the form of a graph of the dependence of the intensity

of the transmitted radiation along the length of the sample. [1]

The water-oil saturation is calculated on the basis of Lambert's law, using the linearity of the semi-logarithmic dependence of the X-ray radiation, based on the base scanning points. [2]

In the oil-water system (with oil blocking):

$$S_{W_t} = \frac{\text{Log}(\text{Scan}_t) - \text{Log}(\text{Scan}_{K_o})}{\text{Log}(\text{Scan}_{K_w}) - \text{Log}(\text{Scan}_{K_o})} \quad (1)$$

where: S_{W_t} - current water saturation, fractions of units.;

Scan_t - the current intensity of the X-ray radiation transmitted through the sample;

Scan_{K_w} - x-ray intensity at 100% water saturation;

Scan_{K_o} - x-ray intensity at 100% oil saturation.

The determination of the displacement coefficient of oil and water was carried out in compliance with conditions as close as possible to reservoir conditions.

To saturate the samples, an automatic saturator (AST-600) was used, which allows to automatically select the time of air pumping and saturation pressure for rapid and complete saturation of core samples. To determine the residual water saturation by the semipermeable membrane method, the PLS-200 system with 4 hydrostatic core holders was used, where humidified air was used to displace water.

All experiments, in order to obtain more reliable results (end effects), were carried out on models formed from three to five samples, depending on permeability, where the length of the model reached up to 26 cm.

Injection of reservoir water in the mode of constant flow of 0.1 - 1.5 ml/min, depending on the permeability, after stopping the pumping of the saturating phase (oil) was carried out continuously until the necessary flushing of the pore volume was achieved.

X-ray scanning to determine the current water saturation of the samples during displacement was carried out according to the set time, depending on the washing.

A certain porosity is meant as an open porosity and, accordingly, the mineralogical density of the rock has an apparent mineralogical density if there is a closed porosity in the sample under study.

The absolute permeability of the samples was measured using gas (nitrogen) on calibrated ULTRAPERME 600 equipment equipped with the latest mass flow meters and pressure sensors. The software performs calculations using the Darcy and Klinkenberg equations to calculate the gas permeability and the inverse of the average pressure.

To measure the grain volume of the samples, a calibrated helium porosimeter (ULTRA-PORE 300) was used, acting on the principle of Boyle's law (2) [3]

$$P_1 \cdot V_1 = P_2 \cdot V_2 \quad (2)$$

The equation used to calculate the grain volume is derived from the basic equation of Boyle's law as follows:

$$P_1 \cdot V_{Ref} = P_2 \cdot (V_{Ref} + V_{Матрицы} - V_{Зерна}) \quad (3)$$

where: P_1 - pressure in the comparison chamber; V_{Ref} - volume of the comparison chamber, cm³; P_2 - pressure after diffusion of helium in the core cup; $V_{Матрицы}$ - core cup volume, cm³; $V_{Зерна}$ - sample grain volume, cm³.

Further, the porosity (4), bulk density (5) and mineralogical density (6) of the rock sample were calculated using the following formulas:

$$\varphi = \frac{(L \cdot \pi \cdot \frac{D^2}{4}) - V_{Зерна}}{(L \cdot \pi \cdot \frac{D^2}{4})} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

$$\rho_{объем} = \frac{m_{обр}}{(L \cdot \pi \cdot \frac{D^2}{4})} \quad (5)$$

$$\rho_{минер} = \frac{m_{обр}}{V_{Зерна}} \quad (6)$$

where:

φ - porosity of the sample, %; L - sample length, cm; D - sample diameter, cm; $\rho_{объем}$ - bulk density of the sample, g/cm³; $\rho_{минер}$ - mineralogical density of the sample (grain density), g/cm³; $m_{обр}$ - dry weight of the sample, g.

The basic Darcy equation for calculating gas permeability is as follows:

$$K_g = \frac{2000 \cdot P_1 \cdot \mu \cdot Q_1 \cdot L}{(P_1^2 - P_2^2) \cdot A} \quad (7)$$

where: K_g - gas permeability, mD; μ - gas viscosity, sP; Q_1 - gas flow rate, cm³/s; P_1 - incoming pressure, atm; P_2 - downward pressure, atm; A - the cross-sectional area of the sample is perpendicular, cm²; L - sample length, cm.

Figure 1. Dependence of permeability on porosity

Conclusions. Filtration studies of compositions on core samples were carried out for further work on calculations of methods of reservoir enhancement, such

as hydraulic fracturing, hydrochloric acid treatments, optimization of mechanized fund.

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